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Artificial intelligence in the music streaming value chain: Exploring artists' and users' perceptions on content creation and algorithmic consumption

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ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence (AI) plays a pivotal role throughout every stage of the music industry value chain. In fact, AI has been integral to the value proposition of music streaming platforms since their inception. This research article investigates how AI—and in particular, Generative AI (GenAI)—affects the creation and consumption stages, the two most socially significant components of the music streaming value chain. It explores users' perceptions of the impact of AI/GenAI on their music-listening experience and examines how artists and performers view the role and influence of AI on their position and opportunities within the streaming model. Drawing on the findings from two separate focus groups with users and artists/performers from different geographies and professional development, this study complements industry debates—often dominated by technology companies and record and publishing firms—by providing valuable insights into the perceptions at both ends of the music industry value chain regarding the impact of these technologies on music creation, dissemination, and consumption. As key findings, while users exhibited a nuanced response to AI-generated music, both existing literature and insights from artists and performers suggest that AI may further amplify the endemic dysfunctions of music streaming platforms, arising governance issues and ethical concerns, particularly regarding to transparency. In addition, both groups highlighted a significant paradox: while AI has the potential to democratise music creation by lowering barriers to entry, it also poses a threat to the existing ecosystem of music professionals, which have relevant implications in terms of the role of culture in societies, policy and practice.

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1. Introduction

“The unlicensed use of creative works for training generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a major and unjust threat to the livelihoods of the people behind those works and must not be permitted.” This statement formed the core of a protest letter launched in October 2024 against the unauthorised use of musical works to train Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) models ([Statement on AI training, 2024](#)). At the time of writing, the letter has already been endorsed by a significant number of music industry organizations and has garnered more than 36,000 individual signatories, including many music creators, artists, and musicians, such as Robert Smith (The Cure) and Björn Ulvaeus (ABBA). The signatories also include writers, actors, conductors, and other creative professionals, such as actress Julianne Moore and novelist Sir Kazuo Ishiguro. Far from being an isolated case, the Artists Rights Alliance also issued an open letter to AI companies, developers, and Digital Music Service Providers (DMSPs), calling on them to “stop devaluing music”. This protest letter was supported by hundreds of artists and musicians, including prominent figures such as Stevie Wonder, Billie Eilish, and Jon Bon Jovi ([Aswad, 2024](#)).

These protests arise within a broader context. AI is significantly and holistically impacting the music industry, playing a crucial role across all stages of the value chain—from content creation to various phases of production, distribution, and final commercialisation ([Arenal et al., 2024](#); [Darvish & Bick, 2024](#)). Indeed, the relationship between AI and the music industry is closely linked to the distribution of music through streaming platforms.

Increasingly central to content creation and monetisation, AI has been integral to the value proposition of music streaming platforms since their inception, underpinning their personalisation and content management capabilities ([Bender et al., 2021](#); [CMA, 2022](#); [Morris, 2020](#)). In practice, AI in music streaming represents a shift from the core value of creative work towards a technology-driven model that reinforces an industry framework whose implementation has been repeatedly questioned ([Butler, 2021](#); [CMA, 2022](#); [DCMS, 2021](#)).

In fact, the emergence of GenAI appears to introduce both challenges and opportunities, particularly in the areas of content creation, consumption, and intellectual property rights. These issues range from the debate over mass access to content for the training of Large Language Models (LLMs) to questions concerning the intellectual property rights of AI-generated derivative works ([Chesterman, 2024](#)). They also include the automation, with increased efficiency, of various phases of creative work, as well as the enhancement of personalized content and adaptive recommendation systems ([Ayemowa et al., 2024](#)).

Additionally, new challenges arise, previously unheard of, such as the increasing prevalence of AI-generated music, which competes with artists’ and musicians’ works and performances on streaming platforms, potentially reshaping perceptions of creative effort ([Stokel-Walker, 2024](#)). From the point of view of rightsholders, AI-generated content also challenges conventions about the copyright framework, not only in the training stage, but also in the configuration of the content supply. For example, in March Sony Music stated that it has already requested the removal of more than 75,000 AI-generating deepfakes of its artists’ content ([Dalugdug, 2025](#)). To compare, the number of requested removal was less than 10,000 in November 2023 ([Stassen, 2023a](#)).

As a result, AI is not only transforming how content is displayed and distributed but also how it is created and produced, disrupting the previously existing, even if unstable, balance of power among key players in the music streaming value chain. While obtaining precise up-to-date and precise figures on the market share of GenAI-generated music is challenging due to the rapidly evolving nature and often opaque proliferation of such content, streaming platforms and rightsholders confirm their relevance. For instance, Deezer informed in April 2025 that roughly 10,000 fully AI generated tracks are delivered to its platform every day, what involves that around 10 % of the daily content deliver to Deezer is generated by GenAI tools ([Deezer, 2025](#)).

Currently, most public debates and analyses of AI’s impact and future sustainability are primarily conducted from the perspective of digital platforms and technology companies, as well as that of rights holders (such as publishers and record labels). However, there is a noticeable lack of in-depth examination of its consequences from the viewpoints of the two extreme ends of the value chain: artists and performers (creative supply) and users (demand side). Moreover, empirical work that jointly contrasts artists’ and users perceptions remain scarce, and evidence on their similarities and/or differences is still limited.

These are particularly relevant issues, given that music is widely recognised as an essential artistic expression of human beings. It plays a crucial role in human cognition, it is deeply intertwined with culture in every society, and serves as a fundamental form of expression across all social groups ([Alhassan & Ridwan, 2023](#); [Cross, 2001](#); [D. Rose et al., 2017](#)).

Therefore, there is an opportunity to explore more deeply the perspectives and challenges faced by these two key components of the music industry value chain. This exploration can provide a stronger foundation for assessing future policy and industry interventions beyond the industrial players’ debate. Within this context, the aim of this article is to shed light on the perceptions of creators and users in the ongoing redefinition of the music streaming distribution model, driven by the disruptive impact of AI, particularly GenAI.

This research adopts a qualitative approach, integrating both primary and secondary data sources. The fieldwork for primary data collection is based on two separate focus groups, each representing a key component of the music streaming value chain: artists and musicians (supply side) and users (demand side).

As a result, the authors of this paper expect to provide valuable insights into the perceptions of both ends of the value chain regarding the impact and significance of AI on music creation, dissemination, and consumption. It explores how GenAI reshapes the creative process, influences creators’ relationships with distribution platforms, affects the discovery and recognition of musical works by users, and transforms the music listening experience itself.

Following this introduction, the paper is structured into five sections. The second section describes the methods and samples used for the analysis. This is followed by the research context on the intersection between GenAI and the disruption of music consumption (Section 3), which precedes the discussion of results (Section 4), the study’s main conclusions (Section 5) and the limitations and potential future research avenues (Section 6).

2. Methodology

This study combines secondary source research with fieldwork to incorporate primary data from the two main components of the music value chain: artists/performers (supply side) and users (demand side). Secondary sources include academic papers and professional reports from the music sector. Fieldwork consists of two focus groups, involving both users and artists/performers (both professional and amateur).

Secondary sources served four roles: (1) to frame the research problem and define constructs; (2) to inform the design of the discussion triggers; (3) to triangulate and contextualize patterns emerging from participants' narratives; and (4) to benchmark our findings against ongoing policy and market developments. Primary data from the two focus groups constitute the core evidence for answering RQ1–RQ4. Following Miles and Huberman (1994), analysis relied on iterative and constant comparison between artists' and users' accounts. Integration was operationalized as analytic triangulation: discrepancies or convergences between groups were examined against the secondary record, which we used to refine categories and to avoid over-generalization from single quotes.

Current literature on the impact of AI-generated music on users and the music industry remains in its early stages and is therefore still limited. Within this body of work, studies that extend beyond the technical dimension to focus on audience and musicians' perceptions are even scarcer. Existing research, primarily based on surveys and experiments with audiences, indicates a general lack of confidence in the creative capabilities of AI (Candusso, 2024; Shank et al., 2023; Tigre Moura & Maw, 2021). Early findings suggest low purchase intentions for AI-generated music and negative credibility perceptions of musicians using AI (Jacobs, 2025; Tigre Moura & Maw, 2021). Meanwhile, experimental studies report no significant differences between audiences and authors in attributing influence to awareness of automation usage (ibid.; Shank et al., 2023).

However, while these findings are indicative, they remain partially premature, as only two of these studies specifically examined fully operational GenAI tools (Correia, 2024). Furthermore, their research questions predominantly focus on emotional responses and binary insights, such as like/dislike, trust/distrust, or simple measures of purchase intention for AI-generated music and the likelihood of using AI tools for music creation (Lac & Tigre Moura, 2024; Shank et al., 2023; Tigre Moura & Maw, 2021).

When integrated into the value chain of the music streaming industry, the implications of GenAI extend far beyond efficiency in mimicking human creations, influencing taste, or shaping purchase potential. Its transformative power extends beyond consumer preferences and creative utility, although these factors are certainly included.

Given that the implications of GenAI for the music industry represent a nascent and rapidly evolving field of inquiry, a qualitative methodology was deemed most appropriate. This approach facilitates an in-depth exploration of the complex and subjective perceptions held by artists and users (Creswell & Poth, 2016), which are critical to understanding the human dimensions of this technological disruption. At this stage of knowledge development, quantitative methods, while valuable for other research objectives, would be less adept at capturing the richness and contextual nuances inherent in these initial explorations of an emergent phenomenon. In this particular case, we argue that a qualitative approach is essential to preliminarily capture the key nuances that shape users' and musicians' perceptions of both the current and anticipated possibilities of GenAI in music creation and consumption. In addition, given the emergence of this theme and the necessity of obtaining feedback from two distinct groups within the music streaming value chain, we have selected the focus group method as our research technique. Focus groups have been extensively examined from an academic perspective, particularly in the study of evolving challenges within the digital media industry, where this approach has proven to be highly effective (Jenkins, 2006). Indeed, some scholars propose that focus groups can serve as an effective method for examining the fundamental processes underlying the formulation of ideas (R.A. Krueger, 1994). One of the main advantages of focus groups is the interaction among participants, enabling them to present their perspectives while contrasting them with those of other group members (Acocella, 2012). This makes it possible to identify both consensus and dissent on a specific phenomenon, articulating subjective perceptions with the shared social discourse on the phenomenon (Jenkins, 2006). Additionally, such exchange encourages participants to articulate their viewpoints with greater precision, which is particularly valuable when gathering primary data on emerging topics. Therefore, focus group method was specifically selected due to its capacity to elicit a rich tapestry of perspectives on a novel and potentially contentious topic like GenAI. The interactive dynamic allows participants to build upon, challenge, and clarify each other's viewpoints, which is particularly valuable for uncovering shared social constructs and points of divergence regarding to the role of AI in music creation and consumption.

To this end, the qualitative findings of this study are based on feedback from two separate focus groups. Specifically, the participants consisted of (i) a group of 10 music users ($N = 10$); and (ii) a group of 8 artists/performers ($N = 8$). The artist/performer sample relied on purposive maximum-variation sampling across three predefined axes to ensure a diverse range of perspectives. At

Table 1
Codification and attributes of participants in focus group 2 (artists/performers).

CODE	ROLE	RANGE	PROFESSIONALISM
Man, 28	Performer	International	Professional
Woman, 46	Artist	Local	Semiprofessional
Man, 47	Artist	Local	Amateur
Man, 36	Performer	International	Professional
Man, 43	Performer	International	Semiprofessional
Man, 33	Artist	Local	Professional
Man, 54	Artist	Local	Professional
Man, 65	Performer	International	Professional

implementation level, we have considered key aspects related to the complexities of using focus group as a research technique (Acocella, 2012). Recognizing potential limitations of focus groups, such as the risk of dominant voices or conformity pressures, the moderation strategy was carefully designed to foster an inclusive environment. This involved encouraging contributions from all participants, ensuring respectful dialogue, and employing probing questions to explore a full range of opinions, thereby mitigating potential biases and promoting authentic expression of individual perspectives (Kitzinger, 1995; Stewart & Shamdasani, 2017).

Looking into the groups, participants in each focus group have similar experience towards the themes discussed to avoid ambiguities, but balancing with not to have excessively homogeneous groups to facilitate the collection of different opinions and perspectives (Kitzinger, 1995; R.A. Krueger, 1994). In the case of the artists/performers' group, while all shared the common experience of being music creators, the deliberate inclusion of varying professional statuses and scopes (see Table 1) ensured a breadth of insights. This strategy aimed to prevent a narrow, single-perspective view while still allowing for a shared foundational understanding of industry dynamics, thereby enriching the data relevant to the study's diverse research questions.

The key issues explored in this study relate to the influence of AI on participants' ability to create, discover, and experience music—whether through creation and production (artists/musicians) or consumption (users). Drawing on Amabile's adaptation of Bourdieu's social capital dimensions in the context of creativity, these aspects have been framed into four distinct dimensions, allowing for a structured analysis of participants' responses (Amabile, 2018). Specifically:

1. The cognitive/sensitive dimension: This dimension encompasses insights related to the experience of creating, interpreting, and listening to music, including aspects such as meaning, emotions, feelings, and sensations, as well as technique, skills, and aesthetics.
2. The structural dimension: This dimension concerns the arrangement of the musical experience, whether through listening or creation/interpretation. It includes elements such as sceneries, rituals, symbolisms, tools, actions, and routines.
3. The functional dimension: This dimension examines the operational consequences of GenAI's use in relation to other players in the value chain.
4. The relational dimension: This dimension focuses on the societal perspectives that participants provide regarding their experiences of music listening and creation in the context of GenAI.

Accordingly, the guiding research questions for both focus groups were:

- RQ1: [cognitive/sensitive dimension] How does AI make a difference?
- RQ2: [structural dimension] Which (and how) AI-related elements or aspects alter key processes/outcomes?
- RQ3: [functional dimension] Which (and how) AI-related factors introduce uncertainty?
- RQ4: [relational dimension] Which are the societal implications for the music experience?

The group dynamics were structured around two discussion triggers, designed to stimulate debate across the four identified dimensions. First, participants listened to a set of six music fragments from different styles (indie-folk, classical music, and country music), four of which were created through multiple iterations using Udio, a "text-to-audio" AI tool, while the remaining two were original compositions by individual artists/composers. For Trigger 1, participants were asked to identify which tracks they believed were AI-generated and to justify their choices. After revealing which tracks were artificially generated, they were also invited to share their impressions of these works.

Trigger 2 involves the presentation of a hypothetical new app, called "InViVo", which is designed to create songs tailored to the user's mood and situation based on biometric data, social networks activity, location, and other collected information. In this case, participants were asked to share their opinions on the product, including the advantages and disadvantages they perceived in its value proposition, whether they would be willing to pay for such a service and under what conditions, and how they believed it would impact the music industry.

In practical terms, the two focus groups were conducted during the second half of 2024. The first focus group consisted of a convenience sample of 10 participants (7 women and 3 men), ensuring diversity in education and listening habits. Participants were individuals aged 18–36, a demographic typically associated with high engagement in music streaming services and early adoption of new digital technologies. This age criterion, coupled with their self-identification as heavy music streaming users, was intended to ensure participants possessed direct and current experiences with the platforms and algorithmic influences central to this study's research questions.

The second focus group involved a convenience sample of 8 artists/performers, selected from the available contacts in the music industry, through direct contact and/or thanks to the collaboration with representative performers' collective management organizations. Building on Patton (2002), we have applied a purposive maximum-variation sampling across three dimensions: a) geographical scope (local versus international careers); b) professional status (professional, semi-professional and amateur/hobbyist); and role (artists, performers – such as guitarists, background vocals etc -). Participants were identified via direct contacts and through collaboration with performers' collective management organizations and no monetary incentives were offered. Inclusion required active involvement in music creation/performance and distribution via streaming services in the last 24 months. The final artist group comprised 8 participants (see Table 1). Consistent with the principle of information power, our target was thematic richness rather than statistical generalizability. This approach yielded a heterogeneous mix of creative trajectories and socio-economic contexts, summarized in Table 1. Such heterogeneity was deliberately sought to capture a broader spectrum of perspectives on how GenAI might differentially impact artists with varying levels of industry integration, resources, and audience reach.

The combined size of 17 participants sits within the 6–10 per group guideline for interactive focus groups (Krueger & Casey, 2015).

Following the principle of information power (Malterud et al., 2015), the narrow study aim, relative homogeneity within each sub-group, and rich dialogue justified this sample as sufficient.

Therefore, sampling strategy prioritized participants who were information-rich concerning the phenomena under investigation—namely, individuals with active engagement with music streaming platforms (users) and those with direct experience in music creation and performance (artists). This purposive approach aimed to maximize the depth and relevance of the data collected from each participant and group, thereby facilitating a comprehensive exploration of the research questions. As a consequence, the sample sizes for the user group (N = 10) and the artist/performers’ group (N = 8) were determined not by aims of statistical generalizability, but by the guiding principle of thematic saturation (Hennink et al., 2016). Consistent with previous research (Krueger, 2014; Malterud et al., 2015; M. Q. Patton, 2015), we argue that information power of our samples is adequate considering our exploratory approach. As participants are information-rich, data from both focus group are sufficient to address the study’s specific research questions while laying the groundwork for broader quantitative follow-ups.

By default, all responses are treated confidentially and included anonymously in the paper, unless the interviewee explicitly grants permission for their name to be mentioned as a participant and/or associated with their responses. The data analysis follows the framework proposed by Miles and Huberman (1994). It is the result of an iterative process, incorporating artists’/performers’ and users’ responses, alongside a continuous review of relevant literature from both academic and industry sources. Evidence from participant contributions is presented in highlighted text throughout the paper, serving as both supporting data and context for the analysis and discussion.

3. Generative Artificial Intelligence and the disruption of music consumption

The relationship between the music industry and AI dates back to the beginning of the streaming era. In fact, the value proposition of music streaming platforms is built on AI-driven capabilities for personalisation and content management (Arenal et al., 2022). Indeed, AI-generated recommendations contribute to at least 30 % of music consumption on Spotify, the leading music streaming platform already in the year 2023 (Ng, 2024).

Similar to other industries, the rise of GenAI introduces new challenges, in the case of the music industry particularly in the areas of content creation, consumption, and intellectual property rights. These challenges include debates over creativity and authorship, the training of LLMs, competition between human-created and AI-generated works, and the need to define relationships among these elements, including their implications for cultural sustainability.

All of these interactions and impacts can be analysed from a value chain perspective (Castro-Martínez; et al., 2013) to provide a framework for discussion meaningful for the different stakeholders’ perspectives and avoid isolated, and biased, debates. Building on previous research, the music streaming value chain can be defined as the interconnected stages in the journey of a musical or artistic work, encompassing its creation and performance, followed by production and post-production, distribution to audiences, and eventual consumption (Arenal et al., 2024; Darvish & Bick, 2024), as illustrated in Fig. 1.

From a value chain perspective, streaming represents a shift from the core value of creation and production (prior to the streaming era) to a technology-driven model enabled by AI (Castle & Feijoo, 2021; Darvish & Bick, 2024). Indeed, music distribution and consumption through digital streaming platforms exhibit specific characteristics that should be considered, particularly regarding the active and dynamic behaviour of contemporary users—who, more than previous generations, are accustomed to actively engaging with content within the broader digital environment (Aguado et al., 2017).

It is important to remind that, beyond value chain economics, music’s deeply personal and experiential nature makes it a uniquely integrated form of identity expression in everyday interactions. That integration has traditionally been a core part of music industry’s

Fig. 1. Primary activities and key actors in the music streaming value chain. Source: Arenal et al. (2024).

value proposition, which also applies to music streaming platforms and their emphasis in technology. How the value creation process addresses and shapes the music listening experience involves considering these aspects from both the supply (artists, producers, and industry professionals) and demand (listeners, users, and digital audiences) perspectives.

From the supply side, music streaming platforms—unlike their audiovisual counterparts—are characterised by a lack of differentiation in the nature and volume of available catalogues across competing services (Antal et al., 2021; Castle & Feijoo, 2021). At the same time, streaming platforms theoretically democratise access to a wide range of music styles and genres. However, algorithmic and editorial curation tend to amplify mainstream trends, leading to a homogenisation of consumption patterns (Born et al., 2021; Senfleben et al., 2022). GenAI introduces new complexities, such as the use of these tools during the creative process and the training of AI models on copyrighted content without the consent of rights holders (Heikkilä, 2024; Stassen, 2024). The latter is particularly concerning, given that some GenAI companies have already scraped all publicly available music from the internet (King, 2024).

From the demand side—that is, from the users' perspective—GenAI complicates certain streaming dynamics and introduces significant changes to key aspects of music streaming access and consumption, including: a) the overload of music supply; b) new competition for artists and musicians, as well as shifting consumer perceptions; c) challenges in content discovery; d) the impact on music diversity. The following subsections provide an overview of these changes in streaming dynamics from the perspective of music consumption.

a) The overload of music supply

GenAI is transforming both the nature and volume of available music offerings. The influx of soundtracks generated using these types of tools—for instance, via text-to-audio programs such as Udio or Suno, which can create songs from detailed descriptions—has the potential to significantly expand the inventory of streaming platforms (Jeans, 2024), which are already under strain (Stassen, 2023c).

As the literature demonstrates, the overload of music supply is a direct consequence of the music streaming business model. The pro rata distribution scheme creates perverse incentives that impact music streaming platforms, rights holders, and creators (Alaei et al., 2022; IPOL, 2023; Moreau et al., 2024). This is, first and foremost, a governance issue for streaming platforms, as they face rising costs associated with managing vast amounts of data and serious side effects, such as unethical or fraudulent practices (Leight, 2023; Stassen, 2023b). However, the problem extends beyond platforms. Rights holders—including major labels—and creators also face significant challenges, given that AI-generated tracks compete for the same pool of monthly income (Cooke & Taylor, 2024). If AI-generated content increases its share of the revenue pool, the financial consequences for human artists are inevitable (McEvoy, 2025).

However, the overload of AI-generated content also affects demand. The increasing difficulty in distinguishing between AI-generated and human-created tracks raises critical questions about the authenticity of the listening experience. Additionally, it sparks complex debates on intellectual property protection, encompassing issues such as the use of copyrighted songs for algorithmic training, plagiarism, and impersonation (Chesterman, 2024; Sturm et al., 2019).

Beyond economic and legal concerns, as mentioned previously, this is also a significant cultural issue. Algorithms designed to optimise content based on user preferences and behavioural patterns may modify, filter, or adjust original historical and cultural materials, distorting their authenticity. Over time, the cumulative impact of these modifications, combined with the vast production of similar AI-generated works, could gradually reshape the historical record, obscuring or even erasing original compositions. This could result in a misrepresentation of cultural and historical truths, weakening the connection between future generations and their artistic and musical heritage.

Ultimately, AI-driven content modifications and the overproduction of similar musical works could contribute to the erosion of collective memory and undermine efforts to preserve cultural and historical integrity.

b) New competition for artists and musicians and shifting users' perceptions

One of the main challenges is that AI-generated music competes directly with traditional musicians, artists, and groups, while users often struggle to distinguish between AI-generated and human-created tracks within streaming platform catalogues (Lema, 2024; Stokel-Walker, 2024).

This presents a significant issue, as users value both the creative process and the final output. On the one hand, listeners demand transparency regarding whether AI has been involved in the creation of cultural content (Batlle-Roca et al., 2024; Brüns & Meißner, 2024). On the other hand, audiences are generally less likely to trust or engage with AI-generated music, regardless of whether they are music professionals or general consumers (Tigre Moura & Maw, 2021).

As a result, AI-generated music faces a major challenge in establishing emotional resonance with listeners. Even when consumers recognize AI-produced music as technically proficient, many highlight the absence of a 'human touch'—a quality traditionally associated with musical artistry (Oksanen et al., 2023), even if it becomes increasingly difficult to identify such a difference unless the AI-based content is labelled as such.

These issues are not new in the context of music distribution and consumption through streaming platforms. Platform and algorithmic opacity have long been recognised as significant challenges for society and culture (Hesmondhalgh et al., 2023). In particular, three key areas have been identified where music streaming services must address their lack of transparency issues: user information and empowerment; the nature and function of curation and recommendation technologies; monitoring and evaluation systems (Born et al., 2021).

In this context, AI-generated content introduces new challenges related to transparency, particularly for users and artists. There is a widespread lack of public understanding not only regarding the distribution side—that is, how algorithmic recommendations work and how they influence final consumption—but also concerning the creative dimension. This raises critical questions about how cultural content is created and produced, who the people, systems, and tools behind the creative process are, and what remuneration schemes apply when AI-generated content is distributed through music streaming platforms.

c) Challenges in content discovery

The indiscriminate upload of AI-generated tracks, often without clear identification, further complicates content discovery for users and inventory management for streaming platforms. As AI-generated music accounts for an increasing share of streams, it diverts economic resources away from conventional artists and contributes to the devaluation of the creative process, as highlighted by various artist protests (Artists Rights Alliance, 2024; Aswad, 2024).

This concern has prompted some platforms to implement countermeasures. Spotify, for instance, has adopted two simultaneous strategies: first, raising the minimum annual streams per track required for revenue sharing to 1000 (Spotify, 2023); and second, enhancing the use of GenAI to personalise music content, including the generation of playlists tailored to user profiles (Spotify for Artists, 2023).

In this regard, the role of streaming platforms has been highly controversial, not only in relation to their function as ‘mediators’ (Hesmondhalgh et al., 2023) or the lack of reliable content recommendation and moderation policies (Brøvig-Hanssen & Jones, 2021; Gillespie, 2018) but also due to allegations of secretly promoting certain tracks and playlists to reduce royalty payments to music creators and rights holders (Rose, 2024).

A notable recent example is Liz Pelly’s research on Spotify’s practices, which concludes that the platform’s own editorial playlists are systematically manipulated to include tracks from ‘ghost’ artists under Spotify’s control—without any disclaimer or transparency regarding this practice (Pelly, 2024).

d) The impact on music diversity

Beyond authenticity and the conditions under which musical creations reach users, GenAI exacerbates long-standing challenges associated with streaming platforms. As with other technological advances, policy approaches to GenAI seek to balance innovation with the preservation of cultural diversity and authenticity in artistic expression.

Researchers have warned about the loss of diversity resulting from algorithmic curation and personalisation systems, which make it increasingly difficult to promote minority music genres and styles (Henry et al., 2024). Additionally, certain types of music that do not conform to algorithmic preferences—such as track length or structural composition—face greater barriers to visibility (Anderson et al., 2020, pp. 2155–2165). As mentioned, these challenges reflect ongoing debates about the structural limitations of music streaming models (Antal et al., 2021; Arenal et al., 2022; Henry et al., 2024), which are further exacerbated by the rise of GenAI.

The collective lack of agency in how recommendation algorithms shape content distribution in terms of diversity is now extending to the content creation stage. The potential homogenisation of creative outputs due to AI’s reliance on existing data raises concerns about diversity and originality (Briot et al., 2020). While advancements in GenAI promise to streamline content creation, enabling new experimental styles and creative outputs, less is known about its unintended social and cultural consequences. At the time of writing, scholars note that GenAI outputs remain highly dependent on training data and, in practice, often replicate existing cultural trends and mainstream influences (Oksanen et al., 2023).

Furthermore, the replacement of human creators by AI could not only erode the livelihoods of musicians and artists but also diminish the cultural diversity of musical works and performances available to the public (Jacques & Flynn, 2024). This concern is particularly significant, given that music is widely recognised as a fundamental form of expression and identity across all social groups worldwide (Alhassan & Ridwan, 2023; Gwervevende & Mthombeni, 2023; Tolmie, 2020; Váradi, 2022).

Overall, AI introduces additional complexity to value creation and value capture within the music streaming value chain, largely due to the growing interdependencies among stakeholders and technologies (Böttcher et al., 2022).

Although numerous studies address issues such as copyright, bias, and the challenges of AI-generated content, there remains a clear gap in the development of comprehensive frameworks that incorporate the perspectives of both artists and users. Current literature often portrays artists and users as passive recipients of technological advancements, rather than as active participants in shaping operating principles, policy approaches, and ethical standards. This oversight risks leading to systems and regulations that fail to account for either the unique challenges faced by individual creators or the perceptions of users.

This pattern mirrors past negotiations on the distribution rules of the music streaming business model, whose sustainability is now widely contested (Arditi, 2019; Arenal et al., 2022; Henry et al., 2024). As previously discussed, debates on ownership and authorship frequently overlook the intricate relationship between human and AI-generated works, which can significantly influence how creative efforts are perceived by audiences.

Furthermore, few studies have examined how audiences perceive authenticity in artistic expression and their emotional connection to AI-generated works, a crucial aspect of balancing technological innovation with the preservation of cultural diversity.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Insights from users

Participants expressed nuanced perspectives on AI's role in music creation and customisation. Their responses reflected a balance between optimism regarding AI's potential and concerns about its implications for creativity, privacy, and human social interaction.

Regarding RQ1 (Cognitive/Sensitive Dimension), which is primarily linked to Trigger 1, participants expressed a mix of skepticism and acceptance toward AI-created music. While some felt that AI lacks the emotional depth and intentionality inherent in human creativity, others acknowledged its technical ability to convincingly mimic human-like compositions. Although most participants were unable to accurately identify AI-generated tracks, they shared similar reasoning in attempting to do so. Key indicators of AI-generated music included a lack of naturalness in vocals and tempos, an 'excessive' level of precision in instrumental performance (such as guitars), and "overly perfect" vocal qualities. Additionally, colour and texture emerged as notable elements used to distinguish AI-generated compositions ("*The voices were very flat, [...] as if they were superimposed*", Man 20).

However, participants attributed these characteristics indiscriminately to both AI-generated and human-created tracks. Their responses reflected an ambivalent stance: while some stated that they "*would feel deceived if they learned a song was AI-created after believing it was human*" (Man, 22), they also acknowledged that some tracks they assumed to be human-made were, in fact, the work of GenAI. Despite this, all participants shared the belief that "*AI can relate to concepts in an original way, but it doesn't reach the human level*" (Man, 36).

Consequently, participants perceive emotional authenticity as a key factor distinguishing human-created compositions from AI-generated ones. However, they struggled to apply this criterion effectively when attempting to identify AI-generated music.

Additionally, they believe that awareness of a song's origin (human vs. AI) influences its perceived value. While AI is acknowledged for its technical innovation in music, it is still seen as lacking the perceived "soul" of human artistry.

RQ2 (Structural Dimension) is primarily explored through Trigger 2, which examines the implications of user-tailored AI-generated music on the music listening experience. Once again, participants express an ambivalent stance: while hyper-personalisation is perceived as both a convenience and a potential threat.

Participants appreciate the efficiency it offers; some view passive consumption as a key factor in the success of the product design: "*I don't have to make the mental effort to look for playlists or anything*" (Man, 20); "*Everything is given to you well chewed up*" (Woman, 19). However, they also express concerns about losing the serendipity of discovering new music and the homogenisation of tastes. As one participant notes, "*It replaces the magic of exploring different artists and enriching yourself culturally*" (Man, 22).

Participants also express concerns about how automation may encourage passive consumption: "*When I saw how the application works, I think that eventually I would return to the traditional way of listening to music*" (Woman, 19); "*[Passive consumption] prevents you from thinking about how you feel*" (Man, 22).

Additionally, hyper-personalisation poses a risk to the diversity of music discovery: "*You lose the magic of music; it gives you everything pre-packaged, and you discover nothing, nor do you identify with an artist or with other people*" (Woman, 19). Participants further express concerns about overreliance on AI-driven content curation and its potential impact on cultural diversity, noting that "*everything sounds similar. It's so easy to anticipate*" (Woman, 32).

RQ3 (Functional Dimension) examines the functional uncertainty-generating implications of GenAI. In the case of users, privacy and surveillance clearly stand out as issues arising concern. Participants expressed hesitation about sharing personal data, citing privacy risks. While some recognised the benefits of customised experiences, noting that "*it provides an emotional connection with the music you listen to*" (Woman, 18), others expressed concerns about the ethical implications and data usage: "*I would not support it because of the data question: who gets the data? Are they sold to record companies? What do they do with the data?*" (Man, 20); "*The application scans you all the time and then makes you a song, ok, but then you don't know what happens to that data, you don't know where it goes.*" (Woman, 19).

Regarding RQ4 (Relational Dimension), which explores how AI-generated songs might influence users' music-related social behaviour, participants demonstrated a clear awareness that AI-generated music could reshape social interactions around music. The social nature of the musical experience and its shareability emerged as key discussion points.

Participants expressed concerns that hyper-personalisation might hinder the ability to share music with others: "*In this case, since it's an experience so tailored to me, I don't know if I could share it with others*" (Woman, 20).

Additionally, there was a common perception that AI-generated music creates an incomplete musical experience due to its lack of referentiality to an artist, thereby diminishing its communicative dimension: "*I can't become a fan of something that doesn't exist.*" (Woman, 18); "*I lose interaction with people (...) and that isolates me more.*" (Man, 20); and "*I lose contact with the musical culture.*" (Woman, 19).

Some participants emphasised that hyper-personalisation is driven not only by customer preferences but also by the commercial interests of streaming platforms: "*Smaller artists are not given visibility in this kind of algorithm-made playlists*" (Woman, 21). Building on this argument, participants generally agreed that AI-powered hyper-personalisation and the increasing presence of AI-generated music on streaming platforms could pose a threat to musicians and their creativity, ultimately leading to a decline in the quality of cultural experiences.

However, a clear distinction emerged between mainstream pressures and personal musical tastes. Most participants believed that the discussed technological advancements still allow room for individual choices: "*These options can coexist as long as there is some pedagogy*" (Man, 36). Some even suggested that, with the rise of AI-powered recommendation systems and artificially generated music, auteur music could become an exclusive domain of elite culture.

Additionally, users expressed a favourable opinion on AI-generated content compensating the creators whose work was used to train the algorithms. However, they remained largely unaware of the legal framework (such as consent) and compensation mechanisms (including payment and credit) applied to issues such as voice duplication.

4.2. Insights from artists/performers

Artists and performers share some of the fundamental perspectives on the cognitive and social dimensions explored with users. However, they also introduce important nuances to the structural and functional dimensions, particularly in relation to their first-hand experience within the industry value chain.

Regarding RQ1 (Cognitive/Sensitive Dimension), artists and performers also emphasised the current limitations of AI in replicating emotional depth, intentionality, and the creativity inherent in human music. Despite some difficulty in distinguishing AI-generated tracks, they expressed skepticism about AI's ability to match the emotional nuance of human compositions: *"AI tools can compose faster, but the result feels mechanical"* (Man, 54). From their perspective, AI-generated compositions feel *"flat"* and *"too perfect"* (Man, 47), lacking the imperfections and expressive nuances that define human creativity. One participant (Woman, 46) referred to AI-generated music as *"meta-creativity"* rather than true creativity.

Several participants also highlighted that AI-generated music may evoke less emotional resonance than human compositions, which are often shaped by a personal narrative or lived experience. As one participant stated: *"It's like the difference between interacting with a replica and engaging with a real person. The function may be the same, but the experience is entirely different. AI-generated songs are not composed from the inside out, nor do they carry genuine emotional depth. In the end, it is merely generating a code rather than creating a song. Developers will try to make it more human, to make it more similar, but ultimately, it remains a process of generating code—it is not truly composing."* (Woman, 46).

However, AI's ability to mimic human creations is perceived by some participants as an imminent threat. While some believe that the human factor will always remain a distinguishing element, others argue that the gap between human and artificial creativity is closing rapidly: *"Now we may recognize them, but in two years, with proper training, we will not see the difference"* (Man, 65).

Correspondingly, discussions around Trigger 2 (RQ2, Structural Dimension) also focused on the possibility of replacing artists with AI composition capabilities. There was a broad consensus on the importance of experience and expertise. Participants generally viewed AI as a valuable co-pilot when used by an experienced musician: *"If you know music, you can make AI work for you rather than against you"* (Man, 43); *"If the prompter is skilled, it can produce surprisingly good results"* (Man, 33).

Participants expressed concerns that AI could replace musicians, particularly in low-budget, mass-market productions such as advertising jingles and ambient music: *"This shift poses a threat to musicians' livelihoods, as AI-generated background music is already replacing human composers in commercials, YouTube videos, and even streaming playlists"* (Man, 65).

However, some participants also viewed AI as a valuable assistant, recognizing its potential to accelerate creative processes. They noted that AI is transforming the creative workflow by introducing new tools for composition, arrangement, and production.

Despite these advantages, participants identified two key risks associated with AI in music creation: dependency and lack of originality. As one participant questioned, *"It's just a tool that gives you speed. The question is: will we use it, or will it use us?"* (Man, 36). Another noted, *"AI can streamline production but can lead to formulaic compositions."* (Man, 54).

Regarding RQ3 (Functional Dimension), participants expressed concerns that AI-generated music, particularly when integrated into streaming services, could lead to reduced royalties and recognition for human artists. Their current experiences with streaming platforms strongly influenced these perceptions.

Participants believed that platforms would likely prioritise AI-generated music to maximize profits, potentially marginalising human artists: *"The industry will invest in AI-generated catalogues because it's cheaper—just like they did with streaming"* (Man, 33). Some even feared the emergence of fully AI-generated artists with no human involvement: *"We're talking not just about AI music, but AI artists—entirely artificial personas taking over the charts"* (Man, 65).

Furthermore, subjects anticipated a deterioration of the problems they already perceive in streaming platforms (Woman, 46). Concerns about the rise of *"artificial artists"* were also linked to fears of music commodification and homogenisation: *"It's going to be all the same shit"* (Man, 43). In addition, participants expressed concerns about intellectual property protection and identity theft: *"Imagine they train an AI to compose like me but rename it 'Juanita.' That's identity theft"* (Man, 28).

The impact of GenAI on the music listening experience and its societal implications (RQ4, Relational Dimension) once again raised the question of musical authenticity. In the view of the respondents, AI-generated music may be convenient, but many doubted its ability to create a lasting emotional impact.

There is a risk that *"listeners may become accustomed to 'junk music'—disposable, impersonal, and algorithmic"* (Man, 28) through personalisation and customisation. However, AI-generated music lacks the human narratives that make artists memorable: *"There's no backstory, no live version to watch, no interviews about how the song was written"* (Man, 33). As one participant noted, *"We become fans of artists, not just songs"* (Woman, 46).

Nonetheless, one participant cautioned that the next generation *"won't care who the artist is" and will consume AI-generated music indiscriminately* (Man, 28). Woman 46 echoed this concern, stating, *"I am convinced that in a few years, there will be a huge market for music made with artificial intelligence. And the worst part is that there will be an audience with no understanding of music who will consume it."*

4.3. Discussion

This study explored how two critical nodes of the streaming value chain, consumers and music artists and performers, perceive

generative GenAI and how GenAI could be reshaping both the supply side and the demand side. Although a growing body of work addresses technological or legal dimensions of this transformation, few investigations juxtapose the lived experiences of creators and users within a single empirical design. By means of two exploratory focus groups we identified four inter-related themes: (1) blurred authorship and performance boundaries, (2) tensions between creativity and efficiency, (3) trust and reliance on platform curation, and (4) uncertainty about future income models. These results show an emergent socio-technical and cultural regime in which synthetic and human creation and performance increasingly co-exist and compete.

From the perspective of listeners, GenAI provokes a paradox between authenticity–usability. Participants reported valuing the “soul” and intentionality they associate with human musicians, yet simultaneously praised the ease with which AI-curated playlists satisfied situational moods and personalized tastes. This ambivalence resonates with cognitive-authority theory, which posits that judgements of credibility are negotiated rather than absolute (Peterson, 2005). Both listeners and musicians realize that identification features of the artificial creation are coherent and persistent independently to whether they refer to an artificial or human performance. This seems to involve a pre-existing standardised discourse around artificial creativity that frames the negotiation of credibility. Users also appeared willing to outsource aesthetic discernment to recommender systems, but privacy issues emerges regarding to the use of personal data.

By contrast, artists’ revealed a pronounced opportunity–threat duality. On the one hand, GenAI was framed as a productivity multiplier enabling rapid prototyping, intervention at multiple stages of the creative workflow, and access to production quality that previously required more expensive resources. On the other, participants expressed anxiety that an exponential surge of low-cost content could cause an unfair competition, dilute revenue pools and erode symbolic capital, a concern consistent with creator-economy scholarship emphasizing precarious labour markets (Watson & Leyshon, 2022).

Several performers also highlighted how GenAI tools have been trained without consent by rightsholders and calls for transparent labelling of AI co-creation invoke longstanding debates over moral rights and attribution, now reinvigorated by policy debates and legislation processes around the world.

A comparative reading of both datasets indicates that both groups value transparency in labelling AI-generated works yet differ in perceived threats: while users fear loss of “soul” and privacy issues, artists also fear loss of livelihood and add the risk of commoditization of music. Interestingly, confidence in detecting GenAI is higher among artists, but objective performance does not differ comparing both groups. This could suggest a gap between overconfidence bias and opportunity for further research.

Beyond music, the patterns we observe mirror dynamics in other creative sectors. First, algorithmic intermediation drives visibility and demand shaping across markets: recommender systems in video streaming and social media feeds, as well as search and rank in ecommerce marketplaces, all reproduce feedback loops that amplify incumbents while narrowing exposure for smaller producers—closely paralleling artists’ concerns about discovery in music. Second, provenance and authorship disputes around generative outputs are not unique to audio: writers, visual arts, filmmakers, performance and theater artists or journalists, among others face similar labelling and attribution frictions, where imperfect disclosure of AI involvement erodes credibility and blurs accountability. Third, value capture moves toward intermediaries: rents concentrate at the recommendation and distribution layers, while creators’ assume higher promotion costs and uncertainty. Situating our findings within these broader patterns clarifies that what appears “sector-specific” in music is better interpreted as a general feature of AI-intensive value chains governed by platform ranking, opaque provenance, and intermediation power.

5. Conclusions

This study explores the evolving role of GenAI in reshaping the music streaming value chain, with a particular emphasis on its impact on both the creative and consumption stages. By integrating insights from the literature and qualitative findings from focus groups with artists and users, this research identifies key tensions, challenges, and opportunities introduced by AI in music creation, discovery, and listening experiences.

The integration of AI in music streaming platforms has disrupted traditional value creation and distribution models, leading to significant consequences for key stakeholders, including artists/performers and users. Both existing literature and insights from artists and performers suggest that AI may further amplify the endemic dysfunctions of music streaming platforms.

The risk of oversupply, for instance, appears to be a direct consequence of governance issues associated with the pro rata distribution scheme (Alaei et al., 2022; IPOL, 2023; Moreau et al., 2024). AI-generated music competes directly with human-created works within streaming platforms’ inventories, creating a challenge in distinguishing between AI- and human-generated compositions (Lema, 2024; Stokel-Walker, 2024).

The emotional connection between the artist and the audience, a fundamental element of the musical experience, is perceived as diminished in AI-generated works. Additionally, oversupply and competition within current distribution models are closely linked to growing challenges in content discovery.

The indiscriminate upload of AI-generated tracks, often not identified as such, further complicates content discovery for consumers and inventory management for streaming platforms (Artists Rights Alliance, 2024; Kjus, 2021). This challenge raises governance concerns, particularly regarding platforms’ evolving criteria for content discoverability. Moreover, it impacts the core value proposition of streaming platforms, as AI-powered personalisation becomes an increasingly distinctive feature, shifting value from artistic creation to technological optimisation.

Simultaneously, AI-driven recommendation systems and personalisation technologies reinforce consumption patterns, often limiting exposure to diverse musical styles and artists. While hyper-personalisation is perceived as convenient, concerns have emerged regarding the erosion of cultural serendipity, the homogenisation of music inventories, and the loss of cultural diversity (Henry et al.,

2024).

Beyond governance issues, ethical concerns also arise, particularly regarding transparency—notably the opacity of AI usage in music creation and recommendation—and privacy, including questions of data ownership and the potential misuse of personal information.

The results of the focus group discussions reinforced the concerns outlined above, providing detailed perspectives from both users and artists. From the viewpoint of artists and performers, one of the primary concerns is the potential displacement of human creativity by algorithmically generated content. Both users and artists, even if they cannot distinguish between them, highlighted that AI-generated music often lacks the depth of human emotion and the personal touch that artists bring to their work.

While some musicians view AI as a valuable tool for enhancing creativity and streamlining production processes, others fear that its widespread adoption could lead to the devaluation of musical craftsmanship and a decline in opportunities for human composers and performers. Again, ethical concerns regarding intellectual property and authorship remain unresolved, particularly as AI systems trained on vast datasets may inadvertently appropriate existing musical styles without proper attribution or compensation.

Users, on the other hand, exhibited a nuanced response to AI-generated music. While some appreciate its potential for personalisation and its ability to generate content tailored to specific moods or contexts, others express skepticism regarding its authenticity and emotional resonance.

The study found that many users perceive music as a social and cultural experience, one that is deeply intertwined with human expression and artistic identity. The absence of a tangible artist behind AI-generated tracks raises concerns about the long-term sustainability of music consumption patterns, particularly in an industry where fan engagement and artist branding play a crucial role.

Additionally, the rise of AI-powered recommendation and content-generation systems has raised concerns about the homogenisation of music. The increasing reliance on AI-driven algorithms to curate playlists and generate new compositions risks reinforcing existing biases and limiting diversity in musical expression. The study participants emphasised the need for AI to complement, rather than replace, human creativity, advocating for a balanced approach that preserves artistic integrity while harnessing AI's capabilities.

A key issue that emerged in the discussion is the potential economic restructuring of the music industry. The adoption of AI-generated content by streaming platforms could lead to a shift in revenue distribution, favouring technology companies over traditional artists and even rights holders. This shift could exacerbate existing inequalities within the industry and highlight the need for new regulatory frameworks to protect the rights of musicians and composers.

Finally, the focus groups highlighted a significant paradox: while AI has the potential to democratise music creation by lowering barriers to entry, it also poses a threat to the existing ecosystem of music professionals. The future of music streaming will therefore depend on striking a delicate balance between embracing technological advancements and safeguarding the cultural and economic value of human creativity.

Taken together, our findings provide an integrated account of how GenAI is reshaping both sides of the music value chain. By juxtaposing creators' and users' perceptions within the same design, we surface not only well-known opportunities and risks but also a set of interlocking mechanisms—the authenticity-usability paradox, shifting trust in platform curation, and income-model anxiety—that help explain why adoption remains ambivalent. These insights move the debate beyond single-stakeholder or purely technical accounts and speak directly to questions of platform governance, compensation, and cultural diversity.

Furthermore, by identifying four interconnected themes—blurred authorship, the creativity-efficiency tension, trust in platform curation, and income model uncertainty—this paper offers a holistic framework for analysing the systemic impact of GenAI. Crucially, this research posits the music industry as a early-warning system for the creative economy at large. The patterns of disruption, platform dependency, and policy dilemmas observed here offer a vital insights for other creative sectors such as film, publishing, and journalism, which are now confronting similar challenges. Consequently, the insights generated are of direct relevance to policymakers tasked with navigating the complex governance of AI in the broader cultural and media landscape.

6. Limitations and future research

While this study provides valuable in-depth insights into artists' and users' perceptions of GenAI in the music streaming value chain, certain methodological considerations could be remarked. The qualitative, exploratory nature of this research, while ideal for uncovering nuanced perspectives in an emergent field, means that findings are not intended to be statistically generalizable to broader populations of music artists or users. Instead, the study offers transferable insights that illuminate the experiences, concerns, and emergent understandings within these specific, information-rich groups. Besides, as with all focus group research, the data collected are shaped by the group context and the interactional dynamics among participants. Efforts were made during moderation to foster a balanced discussion, encourage contributions from all individuals and obtain diverse viewpoints; however, the perspectives shared are inherently situated within that specific group setting and may not fully represent views individuals might express in other contexts.

Particularly, the main limitations of this study stem from the nature of the sample, which was restricted to artists and performers on the supply side and users on the demand side. Findings are context-bound and the two focus groups do not claim statistical generalizability but rather generate theoretical propositions. Perceptions of GenAI and the impact in music streaming value chain may evolve rapidly as exposure increase, so further research is needed to monitor new developments and perceptions.

In addition, the scope of this study was intentionally focused on the perceptions of artists/performers and users. These groups represent two critical yet often underrepresented perspectives in public and industry debates that are frequently dominated by technology companies and established rights holders. While this focus inherently excludes other important actors in the music value chain, it allowed for a deeper and more nuanced exploration of the lived experiences and anticipated impacts at these two key nodes of the value chain. Future research, as outlined subsequently, should indeed broaden this scope to incorporate other stakeholder

perspectives from the supply side (e.g. technical professionals involved in pre- and post-production stages, including mixers and mastering engineers; rightsholders such as record labels and/or publishers; collective management organizations; or even policy-makers). Moreover, on the demand side, the perspectives of cultural agents, civil society at large, and policymakers require deeper exploration, particularly in light of the influence in society models and the extraterritorial effects of copyright-related legal provisions.

Finally, future research should deploy cross-cultural comparison and mixed methods designs with larger samples to test and refine the typologies and themes identified here. For instance, comparative designs that sample creators and/or users from different countries would allow to observe specificities and conventions (i.e. legal issues such as copyright exceptions; or consumption considerations such as streaming platform penetration rates and market shares) that could modulate perceptions about GenAI and expand.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Alberto Arenal: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Juan Miguel Aguado:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Cristina Armuña:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sergio Ramos:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Claudio Feijoo:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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